

An Evaluation of Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS) in the Indian Retail Setting

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Abstract

A series of article by Parasuraman, Zeithmal, and Berry has traced the development of the theory that attempts to explain how consumer acquires perception of the quality of service firm. Parallel with their theory development, Parasuraman, et al. has experimented with various ways of measuring the hypothetical dimensions of service quality. The latest efforts resulted in asset of scale has designed and named RSQS. This paper describes a validation of the study of 28-items of RSQ scale on organized retail setting in Indian perspective. Exploratory factor analytic were used to explore the dimensionality of the scale. This study evaluates the scale developed in the US and considered valid in organized retail store. This paper addresses how customers view service quality of store in India. The frame work for service quality in the RSQ scale has five dimensional structure include Physical Aspects, Reliability, Personal interaction, Problem solving, Policy, also it has first three sub-dimensions comprise of two sub dimensions each.

Key Words: Service Quality, Retail Service Quality Scale, Scale Validation, Factor Analysis.

Introduction:

Service quality has been seen as critical for service firms to position themselves strongly in a competitive environment (Parasuraman, et al., 1985, Shemwell et al., 1998; Mehta et al., 2000) and also as indicators of business performance (Hurley & Estelami, 1998). When faced with larger, powerful retail competitor, smaller stores could compete by improving service instead of competing on price (Klemz & Boshoff, 1999) concentrating on service quality is seen as critical in markets that offer similar products in the store (Berry, 1995), commonly seen in grocery retail stores. However, improvement of the quality of services requires identification of the service quality attributes - the so-called dimensions- that are important to retail customers. Despite the extensive research into the dimensions used by consumers to measure service quality in the service sector, there is lack of empirical studies on factors of quality improvement strategies (Odekerken-Schröder et al., 2001), especially the service quality dimensions (Dabholkar et al., 1996) for the retail sector. The most famous and well discussed service quality model in the 1990s (Robinson, 1999) –SERVQUAL – by Parasuraman et al, (1985) failed to be fully adopted and validated in a retail setting (Dabholkar et al., 1996, 1996). Service quality measurement of the retail stores, unlike the pure service setups, should include the measure of service quality and product quality as retail stores offer a mix of services and products (Mehta et al., 2000; Dabholkar et al., 1996).

Even though large amount of researcher done the work on subject of critical service quality and the we know the major service quality dimension through SERQUAL model by Parasuraman et al, (1985) but to have its applicability in the exact organized retail format is not there as it was for the other service firms. That is why it is important to understand the service quality and its dimensions for the particular retail format are important for the retailer in today's competitive environment.

Service Quality Measurement

It is difficult to measure service quality as compared to good's quality. The difficulty to measure is due to fewer tangible cues available when consumers purchase services (Parasuraman et al., 1985), fewer search properties, but higher in experience and credence properties (Zeithaml, 1981 in Parasuraman 1985), as compared to goods. It also requires higher consumer involvement in the consumption process (Grönroos, 1984). Researchers operationalize the service quality construct either as a gap between expectation of service and perceived performance of service, or just perceived performance alone (Hurley and Estalami, 1998). On the other hand, service quality dimensions are seen as the criteria to assess service quality (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry, 1985). Feinburg, and de Ruyter (1995) supported this idea as they postulate that the dimensions are instruments for measuring perceived service quality. They also posit that consumer-perceived service quality is usually seen as a multi-dimensional construct. The earliest research on service quality dimensions was done by Grönroos (1984). He found that the perceived quality of a service is affected by the experience that the consumer went through for a service. Therefore, he encapsulated the perceived quality of a given service as the outcome of an evaluation process; a comparison between the consumer expectations of the service with his perceptions of the service he has received. He also pointed that expectation is influence by traditions, ideology, word-of-mouth communication, and previous experience with the service and the consumer's perception of the service itself determines his perceived service.

The present study reports on the construct validity of one to measure this construct, the RSQ scale. This study evaluates the applicability of the RSQS scale developed by Dabholkar, Thorpe and Rentz (1996) for measuring service quality in the Indian specialty apparel store context. The refined dimensions are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS)

RSQS Five main Dimensions

Dimensions	Definitions
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Physical Aspects	The appearance of physical facilities, equipment, appearance of personnel, and communication materials
Reliability	The ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately
Personal interaction	The knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence, individualized attention.
Problem Solving	The willingness to help customers and provide prompt service
Policy	The facilities, caring the firm provides to its customers.

Existing research indicates that consumers satisfied with the store's service quality are most likely to remain loyal. Service quality is being increasingly perceived as a tool to increase value for the consumer; as a means of positioning in a competitive environment to ensure consumer satisfaction, retention and patronage. Despite its strategic importance, Indian retailers do not have an appropriate instrument to measure service quality. This study examined the Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS) developed in the U.S. for applicability to Indian retail. This scale has been found appropriate in a variety of settings - across different countries such as South Africa and Singapore and across a variety of store types such as supermarkets, department stores and hyper stores. The data collected from 150 shoppers at large format retail stores in the city of Surat indicates that the RSQ scale can be used to assess overall service quality levels and for tracking overall improvements over a period of time. Investment in further research to modify the RSQS for application in India is recommended.

The RSQ scale for Measuring Service Quality

The psychometric properties of the RSQ scale have been the subject of considerable research in recent times. Service quality is defined as 'a global judgment or attitude, relating to the overall superiority of the service' (Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, 1988, p16). The SERVQUAL proposes a gap based conceptualization of service quality where the gap indicates the extent to which the service obtained confirms to expectations. In SERVQUAL, both - store service performance and consumer expectations of the store service, are explicitly measured to assess the 'gap'. Conceptually, this gap assessment assumes that the statement of desired attribute levels is the yardstick a consumer uses to assess store service performance (Carman, 1990). Schnieder and White (2004) provide a list of several other yardsticks can be used by a consumer to evaluate store service delivery. Even empirically, several researchers find the performance perceptions to be sufficient in assessing service quality as compared to the gap (Carman, 1990; Angur, Natarajan and Jahera, 1999). This resulted in the adoption of the SERVPERF instrument instead of the gap based measure of SERVQUAL. SERVPERF is the performance battery of SERVQUAL.

Similar to and originating from the SERVPERF, the RSQ scale is a performance based measure of service quality but specific to the retail context. Given the lack of theoretical support, Dabholkar, Thorpe and Rentz (1996) used a triangulation of research techniques to discover the factor structure of service quality. It consisted of phenomenological interviews with three retail customers, exploratory in-depth interviews with six customers and a qualitative study tracking the thought processes of three customers during an actual shopping experience at a store. Combining these findings they proposed a hierarchical factor structure for retail service quality consisting of five dimensions - Physical aspects, Reliability, Personal interaction, Problem solving and Policy. These are also referred to as the second-order factors because they are comprised of several sub-dimensions. Each of the first three dimensions has two sub-dimensions each. These six sub-dimensions, also called the first-order factors which are labeled as

Appearance, Convenience, Promises, Doing-it-right, Inspiring confidence and Courteousness/helpfulness.

Method

Participants

The project involved 1 retail store. Business employed both full-time and part-time staff. A firm was owner managed and had operated in the area for many years. The majority of staff was long-term employees and some had family links with the company. In recent years, the firms had faced increased competition from major retail companies, especially through the development of regional shopping complexes and other branded retail malls.

Materials

Prior to administration, minor wording changes were made to RSQS to convert negatively worded items to positive items consistent with the recommendations of earlier researchers (Babakus & Boller, 1991; Parasuraman, Berry, & Zeithaml., 1991). Minor changes were also made to some questions to ensure that the text was familiar to Indian consumers.

Procedure

Data was collected by survey some months after a purchase, the RSQ scale was administered at the point-of-sale by the researchers who was trained in the use of the instruments. Customers were approached only after they had made a purchase from the store. This was to ensure that they were actual customers and not merely “browsers” and therefore familiar with the service of the store they were being asked to evaluate. Customers at firm were asked to give their perceptions of service quality for the 28-items forming the original RSQS scale. All responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale using categories ranging from “strongly agree” (5) to “strongly disagree” (1).

Reliability Analysis

Reliability Analysis address the issues of whether this instrument will produce the same result each time, it is administered to the same person in the same setting.

Table-1. Reliability Statistics

<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
.953	.953	26

Alpha (α) is .953, According to thumb rule of Alpha; we can say that instrument validity is excellent

Table-2. Means, Standard Deviations, and Reliabilities of RSQ Scale

Variable	Item	Mean	S.D.	Alpha
Tangibles	1 to 6	4.213	2.16	.793
Reliability	7 to 11	4.170	2.11	.797
Personal interaction	12 to 19	4.175	2.77	.962
Problem Solving	20 to 22	4.070	1.64	.895
Policy	23 to 26	4.342	1.75	.773

In fact, the descriptive statistics were remarkably stable with the alpha coefficients in each case indicating that the items in the scales were quite homogeneous.

It can be seen that this shortened form of the 28items, contains 26 items with five main items scale.

Exploratory factor analysis is commonly used to help resolve issues of dimensionality. Thus, it may be possible to force a five-factor exploratory solution that yields a loading pattern approximating the hypothesized structure of RSQ scale but that is rather meaningless if the solution does not approach simple structure and if the factors themselves are highly correlated. Confirmatory factor analysis can prove very useful in this situation in that it allows researchers to describe an exact model and test its fit. The technique was employed here for that purpose and indicated that a five-factor model.

Given the challenges already made to the supposed structure of retailservice quality scales, the first stage of data analysis involved the use of exploratory factor analytic routines from the SPSS package to check the dimensionality of the full 26-item RSQ scale. In accordance with the procedures followed by Parasuraman et al. (1991) in their validation study, the principal axis factoring technique was used with the solution constrained to five factors subjected to varimax rotation.

Table-3. KMO and Bartlett's Test

<i>Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.</i>		.870
<i>Bartlett's Test of Sphericity</i>	<i>Approx. Chi-Square</i>	4512.126
	<i>Df</i>	325
	<i>Sig.</i>	.000

KMO measure whether our distribution of values is adequate for conducting factor analysis. Kaiser himself designates level as follows: A measure $>.9$ is marvelous, $>.8$ is meritorious, $>.7$ is middling, $>.6$ is mediocre, $>.5$ is miserable, and $<.5$ is unacceptable.

In this case, KMO value is .870, it is near to .9 so we can say that level of distribution value of data set is marvelous.

Bartlett Test of Sphericity is a measure of the multivariate normality of your set of distributions. It also tests whether the correlation matrix is an identity matrix (Factor analysis is meaning less without identity matrix). A significance value <0.05 indicates that these data do not produce an identity matrix (or “differ significantly from identity”) and are thus approximately multivariate normal and acceptable for factor analysis.

In this case, Bartlett Test of Sphericity is less than 0.05 so our set of distribution is multivariate normal and acceptable for Factor Analysis.

Table-4. Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	12.546	48.253	48.253
2	2.797	10.758	59.012
3	1.777	6.835	65.847
4	1.421	5.466	71.313
5	1.140	4.386	75.699
6	.937	3.606	79.305

7	.785	3.019	82.324
8	.661	2.541	84.864
9	.585	2.252	87.116
10	.468	1.800	88.916
11	.423	1.627	90.544
12	.416	1.599	92.142
13	.360	1.384	93.526
14	.309	1.189	94.716
15	.289	1.113	95.829
16	.233	.896	96.725
17	.197	.758	97.482
18	.172	.663	98.145
19	.127	.489	98.634
20	.104	.400	99.034
21	.083	.320	99.354
22	.060	.229	99.583
23	.048	.184	99.768
24	.037	.143	99.911
25	.014	.055	99.966
26	.009	.034	100.000

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

There are five factors with Eigen values larger than 1.0 and they account near 76% of total variance.

Table-5. Rotated Component Matrix (a)

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Employees intimation</i>	.877	.156	.263	.276	.085
<i>Employees knowledge</i>	.850	.209	.261	.284	.095
<i>Customer safety</i>	.849	.168	.258	.284	.134
<i>Employees promptness</i>	.828	.200	.312	.339	.103
<i>Employees behaviour</i>	.828	.223	.303	.318	.081
<i>Employees courtesy</i>	.795	.245	.267	.136	.191
<i>Customer complaints handling</i>	.728	.369	.304	-.016	.110
<i>Employees response</i>	.712	.331	.117	-.030	.081
<i>Problem solving interest</i>	.688	.292	.324	.008	.136
<i>Return & exchange</i>	.483	.406	.280	.042	.199
<i>Individual attention</i>	.475	.453	-.074	.042	.131
<i>Layout for moving</i>	.220	.674	-.013	.148	.151
<i>Convenient parking</i>	.323	.622	.121	.001	.059
<i>Fast & error free transactions</i>	.359	.594	.042	.278	.049
<i>Layout for finding</i>	.216	.579	.385	.279	.178
<i>Cleanliness & Convenient physical facilities</i>	.244	.434	.306	.217	.355
<i>Promised for services</i>	.055	.424	.294	.261	.344
<i>Convenient operating hours</i>	.397	.068	.859	.119	.024

<i>Acceptens of credit cards</i>	.368	.144	.791	.158	.091
<i>High quality merchandise</i>	.410	.060	.790	-.038	-.023
<i>Promised fulfill</i>	.164	.102	.092	.857	.280
<i>Doing it right time</i>	.229	.172	.057	.811	.240
<i>Availability of merchandise</i>	.152	.437	.026	.499	.068
<i>Materials</i>	.145	.130	.232	.388	.379
<i>Physical Facility</i>	.184	.124	.049	.171	.957
<i>Equipments</i>	.093	.183	-.066	.287	.603

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Factor 1: Employees intimation, Employees knowledge, Customer safety, Employees promptness, and Employees behavior we call it as “Staff services”.

Factor 2: Individual attention, Layout for moving, Convenient parking, Fast & error free transactions, Layout for finding, we call it as “Convenience services”.

Factor 3: Convenient operating hours, Acceptens of credit cards, High quality merchandise, we call it as “Confidence on services”.

Factor 4: Promised fulfill, Doing it right time, Availability of merchandise, we call it as “Assurance of services”.

Factor5: Physical Facility, Equipments, we call it as “Physibility of service”.

Conclusion, Implications and Directions for Future Research

The study demonstrated that the customers attach great importance on the reliability, the atmospheric variable (physical aspect), and the policies of the retailer. For organized store to establish or enhance service quality, they have to ensure that staff is intimated and courteous to customers, have the knowledge to answer customer questions and handle complaints effectively and promptly. Personal interaction with employees and atmospheric variables in a store seems to be strong predictor of overall service quality, strong patronage and recommendation of the store to friends. Managements of store should place greater emphasis on the atmospheric and reliability variables in order to enhance service quality perception and trust among customers. While the retailer’s policy may not seem to be a strong predictor of overall service quality, store patronage and recommendations of the store to friends, its value should not be underscored.

Store system must be responsive to the needs of the customer. Store systems such as in-house cash withdrawal facilities, payment of utility bills, safe customer parking are essential availability of merchandise and there layout enhance the service quality and customer satisfaction. The role of technology should not be underestimated. New technology and interactive marketing can create new opportunities for retail store. Retailers can use technology to simplify and improve the service offered to customers like acceptance of credit cards etc.

This study undertaken within the retail store, adds to the growing literature, which calls for the re-examination of how to measure and mange service quality. The result of this study cannot be accepted as being completely relevant and applicable to all retailers who offer a mix of goods and service, because of the limited sample size, the sampling procedure and particularly its focus on store.

Directions for Future Research

The interpersonal category (human element) recorded a number of incidents in the focus group interviews. There would be value in additional work to analyze these incidents further to try to

establish a more detail perspective on key influencing factors impacting on service quality perceptions in retailing. Previous research (Zeithmal, 1988;Sproles, 1977;Stafford &Enis, 1969;Injazz et al., 1994; Yoon & Kijewski, 1997) states that the relationship between quality and price appears to be product specific and generally weak. Should store continue to emphasis low price in their competitive strategies or should they accept the risk of asking to pay a premium for enhanced services?

The development and testing of the store service quality instrument has implications for other goods retailers as well. Based on this study and other studies cited, it appears that and that future research on Service Quality should involve the development of industry specific measure of service quality.

While this research provides some important insights into service quality in organized retailing, there is still an opportunity to extend these findings to gain a more comprehensive understanding of organized retailing. The future research may highlight the service quality in retailing in total, comparative analysis on RSQS scores in different kinds of stores, market segment and formats in retail industry. The future research may be directed to deep analyze the better applicability and enhance the understanding of RSQS in retail industry.

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